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ENHANCING SCREENING AND MANAGEMENT OF DELIRIUM IN CRITICAL
CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

Zenaida K. Co

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Sue Robertson, RN, PhD, CNE, Project Chair
Dana Rutledge, RN, PhD, Committee Member

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ABSTRACT

Delirium is a major health issue for critically ill patients. Delirium is characterized by a change in level of cognition with disorganized thinking, and can result in cognitive impairment if undiagnosed and treated. Without screening, greater than 66% of patients with delirium may go undiagnosed, and cognitive impairment upon discharge is 10-fold higher for undiagnosed patients. Use of the Confusion Assessment Method in Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU) is known to optimize identification of delirium among critically ill patients. Despite staff training and adoption of the CAM-ICU tool in 2014 in critical care units of a southwestern Magnet-accredited faith-based community hospital, chart audits found that unit staff was inconsistently screening and managing delirium. Nurses stated that the tool was complicated and time-consuming.

Following a literature review, an educational program was developed to address the problem. The program is composed of a self-learning module (SLM) with pre- and post-test to be followed by supervised bedside application of the tool, and skills evaluation using a competency checklist. Also developed was a reference and resource manual to be kept on the unit. The program has been approved by the unit manager and clinical nurse specialist (CNS), and will be piloted on five nurses during summer 2018. The five nurses will become the nurse champions for this program. The program will be given to the remaining nurses of the unit after the pilot. A post-program assessment will

determine the prevalence of delirium in the unit, data which has not been available to date.

Enhancing nurses' skill in identifying presence of delirium will optimize the management of delirium in critical care. This educational program for staff should improve patient care for critically ill patients.

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BACKGROUND

Over 3 years ago, nurses in a 26-bed critical care unit adopted the Confusion Assessment Method in the Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU), the gold standard in screening for delirium among ICU patients (Gusmao-Flores, Salluh, Chalhub, & Quarantini, 2012). Despite staff training and adoption of the CAM-ICU, chart audits found that unit staff was inconsistently screening and managing delirium. This created patient safety issues such as falls and ICU doctors using multiple drugs to treat one condition. While nurses may have inadequate knowledge of how to use of the tool, another issue was that on this unit, no standard or guidelines are used for the management of patients who screen positive for delirium.

Delirium in Critical Care Patients

Delirium in critically ill patients is a major public health problem. It affects up to 80% of mechanically ventilated adult ICU patients, and hospital care costs \$4 to \$16 billion annually in the United States alone (Leslie et al., 2011; McNicoll et al., 2003; Milbrandt et al., 2004). Due to the longer hospital stays and required follow-up care in nursing homes, untreated delirium is estimated to cost nationally more than \$143 billion annually (Leslie & Inouye, 2011; Marcantonio et al., 2003).

Commonly seen in acute care, delirium is an acute state of mind that involves the inability to focus along with a change in level of cognition characterized with disorganized thinking. The American Psychiatric Association (APA) defines delirium as

“disturbances of consciousness, attention, cognition, and perception” (APA, 1999). There are three types of delirium: a) hyperactive, b) hypoactive, and c) mixed (Neufeld & Thomas, 2013). Delirium can develop relatively quickly (usually over hours to days) and tends to fluctuate during the course of the day. In hospitalized patients, it is associated with medications (e.g., analgesics or opioids), surgical experiences, or environmental factors. Up to 80% of ICU patients may experience delirium during the course of their hospital stay and their mortality rate is 35-40% (Heymann et al., 2010).

Nurses play a vital role in early identification of delirium among ICU patients. Nurses are present 24 hours per day, and they engage in ongoing assessment of patient mental health status. They are able to respond quickly to changes in patient condition by modifying plans of care. However, surveys have revealed deficits in nurses’ ability to recognize and treat delirium promptly (Flagg, Cox, McDowell, Mwose, & Buelow, 2010).

The CAM-ICU was developed to assist nurses in identifying early signs of delirium. It is especially effective for identifying hypoactive delirium with its subtler signs. Using the CAM-ICU tool can assist in developing an effective treatment plan; however, this screening tool has not been used consistently or correctly by nurses (Eastwood, Peck, Bellomo, Baldwin, & Reade, 2012; Gusmao-Flores et al., 2012). Barriers to its use include the time it takes to complete the tool and its level of complexity. Thus, inconsistency in implementation may be the result of insufficient training.

Statement of the Problem

In 2014, standardization of care was implemented across 14 hospitals in a southwestern health care system. The CAM-ICU tool was introduced to ICU nurses to assist with identifying delirium among ICU patients. After the tool had been implemented for a year in the ICU of the project hospital, a retrospective chart review (2015) demonstrated that 80% of the time, nurses did not accurately complete the tool. Also, CAM-ICU scores did not accurately match signs and symptoms that patients were exhibiting. This performance gap indicated an opportunity for improvement. Attempts to re-assess nurses' knowledge on the use of the tool during an annual Skills Lab exercise (2015) triggered anxiety and resistance. Afterward, informal questioning of nurses (fall 2016) revealed a high percentage did not understand what delirium was and a majority was not comfortable using the CAM-ICU. Nurses stated that the tool was complicated and time-consuming. Most did not appreciate the importance of using the tool in identifying delirium among ICU patients. In addition, nurses did not believe that ICU physicians were appreciative of their efforts to use the CAM-ICU tool, often failing to use CAM-ICU scores to drive treatment decisions. Nurses also complained that there was no existing standard of care for managing patients with delirium.

Nurses constitute the majority of healthcare workers in ICU, spending many hours with patients. In ICUs, nurses should become proficient in use of the CAM-ICU and understand the importance of frequent delirium screening. Nurses' knowledge in identifying potential delirium is vital in patient care. The CAM-ICU can be used to systematically screen patients for delirium (Gusmao-Flores et al., 2012). This tool is helpful in assessing four clinical features: (a) acute change or fluctuation in mental status

from baseline; (b) inattention; (c) altered level of consciousness; and (d) disorganized thinking. Without screening, greater than 66% of patients with delirium may go undiagnosed (Inouye, 2006). As a result, cognitive impairment among these patients at discharge is 10-fold higher than those delirium patients who are recognized and treated at bedside. Furthermore, lack of delirium identification among ICU patients contributes to prolonged hospital stays, increase in complications, unnecessary hospital costs, and increased mortality and morbidity rates (Gusmao-Flores et al., 2012). Improving delirium screening should assist in selection of nursing interventions for delirium and timely reporting to physicians, thus promoting effective treatment.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project is to develop and implement an educational program to teach nurses and the interdisciplinary team (IDT) how to effectively utilize the CAM-ICU tool. Because the tool has already been introduced in the project setting, the project consisted of a re-introduction of the CAM-ICU tool with new education and facilitation methods. The objectives were to:

1. Develop a learning module that addresses problems associated with untreated delirium, the importance of using the CAM-ICU to identify delirium in the ICU, delirium assessment, and nursing management of delirium.
2. Develop a competency assessment checklist.
3. Identify five nurse champions for the ICU.
4. Develop assessments to determine program and learning module effectiveness.

Supporting Framework

The QI project is supported by the integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (iPARIHS) framework. This model has five aspects: Innovation, recipients, inner context: local level, inner context: organizational level, and outer context. According to Kitson and Harvey (2016), each aspect of this framework plays an important role in acquiring new knowledge in order to transform clinical practice (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The promoting action on research implementation in health services integrated framework (i-PARIHS framework): facilitation as the active ingredient (reprinted with permission from Harvey & Kitson, 2015)

Characteristics of the Innovation

Innovation is the new knowledge or practice based on evidence to be implemented at bedside. For an innovation (new knowledge/practice) to be adopted by the targeted recipients, they must understand its characteristics (known through literature

search) and recognize the importance of the innovation. This implies that it is important to deliver information about the CAM-ICU screening tool in a simple, understandable way. Because the CAM-ICU has already been introduced, the fact that this project will be a re-introduction leads to consideration of why the first introduction failed, and how to maximize the chances of success with a re-introduction. During the re-introduction of this tool, supportive evidence and research articles will be presented to assist in nurse understanding the importance of this tool in delivering safe patient care. Trial-ability is a characteristic of this innovation. It is possible to trial the CAM-ICU tool following the education and reintroduction.

Recipients of the Evidence/Innovation

The ICU nurses, physicians, and IDT members are the people whom this innovation is targeting and are considered recipients in the i-PARIHS model. Kitson and Harvey (2016) suggest that to change the way individuals think, facilitators must think about the role of every stakeholder as information is disseminated throughout the implementation process. How recipients respond to new knowledge will depend on several factors: motivation, values and beliefs, skills and knowledge, and time.

This QI project is primarily focused on nurses who as bedside clinicians are responsible for providing safe patient care. An objective is to convey the importance of using the CAM-ICU tool as a screening method for delirium patients and the problems associated with untreated delirium. Understanding the reason for using the tool will help recipients appreciate their role in screening for and managing delirium, and addresses one of the barriers determined to be present for staff nurses in preliminary work. Masso, McCarthy, and Kitson (2014) stress that if recipients (e.g., nurses and IDT members) see

the importance of implementing change, in this case, an evidence-based practice, this will help them gain ownership and control the practice change.

Recipients can be conceptualized as either beginners, experienced, or experts. Involving the beginners (IDT and new hires), experienced (ICU nurses and doctors), and experts (ICU resource and IDT resource) through facilitation of knowledge about delirium and the CAM-ICU tool, will allow all to perform their role and flourish. During facilitation, the facilitators will consider different knowledge and skill levels of the recipients. Thus, the beginners will be mentored and supported during introduction to the CAM-ICU. Following re-training, experienced recipients will be urged to support beginner recipients. Experienced recipients will have worked for period of months as a facilitator learning the skills and techniques of facilitation. Working with the experts, beginner and experienced recipients should begin to understand how and why this innovation needs to be used. The implications of this will include changing the methods used by physicians to treat patients with delirium, and will involve the use of IDT members such as occupational and physical therapists, ICU charge nurses and managers, respiratory therapists and family members.

Recipients are the people who are affected by and influence implementation at both the individual and organizational team level. With the inclusion of local and organizational context, the i-PARIHS framework considers the impact that individuals and teams have in supporting or resisting an innovation. We have elected to consider recipients at both an individual and collective level as well as highlighting the importance of individuals in changing care plans. There is good evidence to suggest that groups or

teams of individuals are important in determining the learning of new knowledge in practice (Kitson & Harvey, 2015).

The Inner Context: Local Level

Kitson and Harvey (2015) defined context in terms of resources, culture, leadership, and orientation of the project site to innovation and learning. These contextual factors have been recognized as important considerations when implementing new knowledge or practice changes. Local context includes the leadership and support shown by the managers for the project. For innovation to be implemented, we need to understand the culture that exists among recipients and management. McCullough et al. (2015) identified leadership, teamwork, and communication as important components necessary for innovation to occur. Carrothers et al. (2013) noted in their site interview data, physician support and hospital leadership support are additional factors that facilitated implementation. Therefore, managers' attitudes towards change can influence the implementation of this screening tool on the project unit. For an innovation to be successfully implemented, the support from the leadership team, the managers in the project site, is considered very important. Good working relationships exist between the manager and staff with staff being committed to using evidence based practices at bedside. But sometimes, with the nature of caring for high acuity patients, nurses have resisted change (e.g., using CAM-ICU) as they considered it to be additional work for them.

Justice is one of the values being advocated by the organization where this innovation will be implemented. The systems and structures are attuned to the needs of the vulnerable and disadvantaged. There is promotion of a sense of community among

all persons. These are the guiding principles for all healthcare workers, shaping the interactions with those whom they are privileged to serve. Justice applies to this project by protecting the right to proper treatment for delirium as recognized in a timely manner by IDT members. This “rationale” supports the need to implement the CAM-ICU as it will lead to improved interactions with recipients.

In preliminary work, nurses identified a barrier in using the CAM-ICU was the absence of unit guidelines to follow when a positive delirium screen occurred. This barrier was addressed during conversations with the ICU physicians. Another barrier identified by nurses was the time needed for using the tool. Evaluation and feedback processes will be implemented during the re-training period, to gain more knowledge of the time needed to implement the tool; re-training should minimize any wasted time.

The Inner Context: Organizational Level

The project hospital is dedicated to providing evidence-based practices to ensure excellent patient outcomes. Several organizational factors support the likelihood that this QI project will be successful. The hospital has its own education and research department that supports employees transitioning to different levels of advance education and professional development. The education department provides assistance with multiple QI and research projects. Also, this organization has an excellent IT department that can help employees with data extraction and report generation.

A strategic priority of this organization is population health management. By implementing this QI project, nurses will be able to utilize effectively the CAM-ICU and recognize early delirium, thus, improving population health. If delirium is recognized early and treated, patients are discharged with no functional disability.

Outer Context

In the initial CAM-ICU introduction and implementation, the potential impact of the environment outside of the health system—the external context— was not considered. Anecdotal evidence suggests that there were problems with implementation of CAM-ICU in other hospitals affiliated with this healthcare system. Re-education about the CAM-ICU will be implemented in this hospital with the hope of extending this knowledge transformation to the other 14 hospitals of the health system. The implementation will not incur any payment or expenses. The CAM-ICU should assist the IDT in identifying delirium at an early stage and with appropriate treatment, save unnecessary treatments for patients.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Methods

A literature review was conducted to obtain information regarding studies related to the use and implementation of the CAM-ICU and the development of educational programs to successfully implement the tool. With the educational focus of enhancing the skills of nurses and management of delirium in Critical Care Unit, the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, and Education Resources Information Center (ERIC) databases were searched using the search terms and phrases: “Confusion Assessment Method in Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU),” “delirium,” “changing provider behavior,” “program implementation to introduce screening in ICU,” “adult learning theory,” “teaching strategies,” and “competency assessment.” The search results were limited to peer-reviewed articles in English and published from 2012 to 2017. The articles included program evaluations, clinical trials, meta-analyses, and randomized controlled trials. The search yielded no CAM-ICU screening articles under CINAHL. The search was expanded to 2005 in order to obtain studies to support the QI project.

For the CAM-ICU evidence, inclusion criteria were studies in which participants were 18 years or older, required ICU care, were diagnosed with conditions related to inattention, or confusion, and were sedated or given analgesics and in which, frequent falls were noted (rationale: meta-analysis conducted by Hshieh et al. (2015) showed a

strong link between falls and delirium). Articles were excluded based on title and subject relevancy and duplications. Studies were examined related to enhanced screening and management of delirium in critical care.

The Education Resources Information Center (ERIC) database was searched to find evidence about how nurses and physicians respond to change, and included articles related to adult learning, and to assessment of new competency, performance, and knowledge acquisition. To address the methods for this project, search terms as self-learning modules, scaffolding, and nurse champions (NC) were explored. The reference sections of all applicable studies/reviews were reviewed in order to retrieve additional related articles. Tables 1- 8 show the search results.

Table 1.

CAM-ICU Screening

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2005- 2017	16	11	5	5
PubMed	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	5	0	5	5

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 2

Educational Program Implementation

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2005- 2017	14	11	3	2
PubMed	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2005- 2017	9	6	3	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 3.

Changing Provider Behavior

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	15	10	5	3
PubMed	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	313	308	5	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 4.

Adult Learning Theory

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
CINAHL	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	6	1	5	3
PubMed	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	159	154	5	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 5.

Teaching Strategy for Complex Information/Higher Education

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
ERIC, CINAHL, PsycInfo	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012-2017	13	8	5	5

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 6.

Competency Assessment

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
ERIC	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	16	13	2	2
CINAHL	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012- 2017	75	73	2	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 7.

Self-learning Modules

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
ERIC, CINAHL, PsycInfo	Peer Reviewed, English Language, Publish Date: 2012-2017	55	44	11	5

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Table 8

Nurse Champions

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
ERIC, CINAHL, PsycInfo	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2012-2017	13	8	5	5

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic.

Delirium Subtypes and Epidemiology

Delirium is a condition with manifestations of mental dysfunction. It is an independent predictor of negative clinical outcomes in ICU patients. It increases hospital length of stay (LOS) and costs of care, and can cause long-term cognitive impairment (Girard et al., 2010; Milbrandt et al., 2004; Shehabi et al., 2010). The ICU team, whose members include nurses, physicians, and therapists, plays a significant role in the identification, prevention and treatment of delirium (Needham et al., 2010; Pandharipande et al., 2007; Pisani, et al., 2009; Riker et al., 2009).

Delirium is a syndrome characterized by four features: an acute onset of cerebral dysfunction with a change or fluctuation in baseline mental status, inattention, and either disorganized thinking or an altered level of consciousness (American Psychiatric Association, 1994; Bergeron, Dubois, Dumont, Dial, & Skrobik, 2001; Ely et al., 2001; Gupta, de Jonghe, Schieveld, Leonard, & Meagher, 2008; Meagher et al., 2011). Patients with delirium may be agitated (hyperactive delirium), calm or lethargic (hypoactive delirium), or fluctuate between the two subtypes. Hyperactive delirium is more often

associated with hallucinations or delusions while hypoactive delirium is more often characterized by confusion and sedation (Ely et al., 2001).

Delirium in critically ill patients is recognized as a major public health problem. It affects up to 80% of mechanically ventilated adult ICU patients, and costs \$4 to \$16 billion annually in the United States alone (McNicoll et al., 2003; Milbrandt et al., 2004). Delirium can be detected in both intubated and nonintubated ICU patients when using valid and reliable tools. In most studies, delirium detection improved when caregivers used a valid and reliable delirium assessment tool (Elliott, 2014; Mistarz, Elliott, Whitfield, & Ernest, 2011; Spronk, Riekerk, Hofhuis, & Rommes, 2009; Tomasi et al., 2012).

CAM-ICU Screening Tool

Nurses and other healthcare workers often underestimate the presence of delirium among inpatients in the ICU because symptoms frequently present as hypoactive rather than hyperactive (Guenther et al., 2010; Peterson et al., 2006). Routinely monitoring ICU patients for delirium using the CAM-ICU tool has shown advantages to patient care such as early diagnosis and prevention of accidental injuries and falls (Eastwood et al., 2012; Elliott, 2014; Mistarz et al., 2011; Tomasi et al., 2012). A study of delirium monitoring implementation that included 500+ ICU patients and 600+ ICU nurses over a 3-yr period reinforced the conclusion that routine delirium monitoring was feasible in clinical practice (Salvatore et al., 2011).

The CAM-ICU and the Intensive Care Delirium Screening Checklist (ICDSC) are two valid and reliable delirium monitoring tools used by healthcare providers for adult patients in the ICU (Bergeron et al., 2001; Ely et al., 2001; Guenther et al., 2010; Hudetz,

Byrne, Patterson, Pagel, & Warltier., 2009; Larsson, Axell, & Errson., 2007; Soja et al., 2008; Tobar et al., 2010; van Eijk et al., 2009). This project will focus on the CAM-ICU tool since it is currently used in the project hospital. With use of the CAM-ICU, patients can be diagnosed with delirium more quickly after the onset of symptoms which leads to early management and decreased severity of delirium (Hasemann et al., 2014).

Staff Training plus CAM-ICU Tool

Mistarz et al. (2011) reported that staff training plus use of CAM-ICU improved detection of delirium at bedside. Bedside teaching was the most popular method of instruction (Mistarz et al., 2011). Balas et al. (2013) found that trained participants reported low levels of confidence in CAM-ICU use even after an educational session. Despite the authors' intention of making the educational session brief (the study did not specify how long was the session), it is possible that there was insufficient information to improve understanding of the topic. Study findings suggest that extended repetitive training could lead to enhanced confidence and thus, higher implementation rates than one-time training. This is different from the educational program developed by the project lead. The program will include a SLM which explains the delirium pathophysiology, knowledge that was identified by nurses to be deficient. Another element of the program was the bedside application of nurses in using the tool with the project lead supporting and making sure that the transfer of skill is appropriate.

Furthermore, since delirium fluctuates in onset and duration, screening should take place several times during hospitalization (Hasemann et al., 2014). In a recent study, Elliott (2014) concluded that 44% of nursing and medical staff were not educated about ICU delirium. Staff identified barriers to using the delirium screening as time constraints

and lack of confidence in using the tool. The SLM will address this problem. The module focused on the problems of delirium and valid techniques for assessing delirium utilizing CAM-ICU. One barrier in use of CAM-ICU was lack of medical support for patients once they screened positive.

Studies show that through use of the CAM-ICU tool, delirium can be identified. However, some physicians believe only they can diagnosis delirium (Carrothers et al., 2013; Devlin, Fong, Fraser, & Riker, 2007). This implies that physician buy-in is necessary for appropriate use of screening findings. Thus, poor physician buy-in of nurse screening of delirium can be a barrier. Successful strategies for overcoming this hurdle require a focus on human factors and changing ICU culture (Brummel et al., 2013). Physician buy-in and management support of nurse-screening of delirium was identified as a contributing factor in successful implementation of the CAM-ICU tool (Balas et al., 2013; Pun et al., 2005; Soja et al., 2008). In a nationwide Dutch telephone survey, Van Eijk, Kesecioglu, and Slooter (2008) found that CAM-ICU was supported by only 14 out of 103 ICU head nurses due to their own lack of knowledge. It is very important that nurses, their managers, and critical care physicians understand delirium and the advantages of the CAM-ICU tool in order to be able to acquire buy-in from all and acceptance of the educational program to be implemented. As a result, the patient's delirium will be addressed accordingly.

Changing Provider Behavior

One of the challenges to implementing change in clinical settings is the behavior of recipients. Changing provider behavior is a very complex process and requires examining things beyond behavior. Kitson and Harvey (2016) suggested consideration of

motivation of providers to change and why should they undertake the innovation.

Whether providers perceive the proposed change as valuable and worthwhile is equally important as the change itself. Grimshaw et al. (2004) reported that most recipients will resist change, and this requires the use of active dissemination and implementation strategies. In their systematic review of changing provider behavior, Squires et al. (2014) identified that the use of multifaceted interventions such as feedback, audits, reminders, and educational outreach tended to change behavior. Behavior changes studied were prescribing behaviors (e.g., reducing the number of prescriptions written for antibiotics) and use of guidelines to improve health related practices and improving hand hygiene. Four studies included in their review found multifaceted interventions to be better compared to single interventions (Squires et al., 2014). However, Squires and colleagues also noted that changing practice using less complex interventions is less expensive and simpler to implement. The behavior of the nurses and IDT play a significant role in the success of the QI project.

Lack of organizational support can be a barrier to behavior change. Interested in their institution's screening programs, Qiu and colleagues (2016) interviewed 13 physicians and nurse navigators, and sent questionnaires to 65 centers providing low dose computerized tomography (LDCT) scans. The barriers to implementation were that few patients were referred by physicians, lack of financial reimbursements from insurance, and lack of social support from some professional organizations. The educational program developed by the project lead will not incur any financial expenses. It's been supported by the ICU manager and CNS for implementation. Furthermore, a systematic review of implementation strategies for assessment, prevention, and management of ICU

delirium and their effect on clinical outcomes was conducted by Trogrlic et al. (2015). This review of 21 studies found that programs which included assessment, prevention, and management of ICU delirium (e.g., promoting adherence to delirium screening and delirium knowledge, audit and feedback) were more effective in clinical outcomes improvements. Implementation programs were more effective when healthcare professionals as well as organizational support were considered (Trogrlic et al., 2015). These barriers were not a problem in the project setting, since the manager and the director of the unit were supportive of the project.

Lineker et al. (2009) suggested that inter-professional learning in activities such as workshops can be a successful way to introduce knowledge and change provider behavior. The multidisciplinary providers in the Lineker et al. study identified team learning, opportunity to network, and involvement of a trained educator as contributing factors to successful behavior change. The project lead adapted team learning and trained educator (nurse champions) in the development of the educational program. Through invitation of nurses into the patient's room and sharing knowledge about delirium as it is actually happening with a patient, is a form of team learning. An aspect of Linker's et al. (2009) findings called "team learning" is an important experience. Through team learning, nurses are able to appreciate the sharing of knowledge and integrating nurses at bedside. A nurse who is able to identify delirium using the CAM-ICU tool is able to share this experience with other nurses and invite them to the bedside of a delirium patient.

DEVELOPING AN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

The literature review conducted by the project lead have been an integral part in developing this educational program, which is aimed to re-educate nurses about delirium and how to use the CAM-ICU. Developing an educational program includes planning activities that facilitate learning. The program has to be developed with the learner as the main focus. It is essential that careful planning be considered for program implementation. It also requires an understanding of adult learning theory. This provides insight into how adults learn and how an appropriate educational format is developed. After identifying the learners (in this project, the nurses in the critical care unit), learning objectives were created based on identified educational needs. The goal of this educational program was to provide needed knowledge and experience for ICU nurses to use the tool in assessing delirium.

In their systematic review, Yanamadala, Wieland, and Heflin (2013) concluded that nurses will recognize delirium through formal teaching that is interactive and is combined with strategies involving participation from learners and using CAM-ICU. The authors further concluded that designing educational programs to enhance the use of CAM-ICU requires taking into consideration how adults learn. Glanz, Escoffery, Elliott, and Neil (2015) described the importance of providing feedback, reinforcement, and skill-building guidance during implementation of a new program. Bradshaw and Lowenstein (2011) stated that educational programs must

employ an on-going strategy that assesses a learner's ability to transfer theoretical knowledge to clinical practice. The results from the review and studies were considered during the development of the educational program. A learning strategy utilized by the project lead was a supervised bedside application, an opportunity for nurses to apply the knowledge at bedside, with feedback from the project lead or a nurse champion. This allows interactive learning to occur. The nurses will be given a laminated CAM-ICU tool to refer to during the bedside application of assessment, and feedback will be given to the nurses by the project lead or nurse champions, which are forms of skill-building guidance and reinforcement strategies.

A study by Carrothers et al. (2013) supported that ongoing access to training using both written and electronic materials, and hands-on supports are factors that enhance learning and successful implementation of the tool. In this doctoral project, a SLM was developed and will be saved as electronic material in the project site's education portal. Nurses will be required to take the module by accessing the education portal. Furthermore, Balas et al. (2013) used resource materials such as CAM-ICU pocket cards during training; these were found to be helpful for nurses as reference guide and were proven effective in the dissemination of the program. As part of this project, reinforcement in the form of a laminated pocket sized CAM-ICU tool (Appendix G) will be given to every ICU nurse as a reference. A resource manual was created and made available in the unit. This resource manual is a binder with important information about the CAM-ICU tool, how it is used at bedside, and topics on delirium.

The format of educational program can affect outcomes of an innovation's adoption. Kozica et al. (2012) identified face to face as the most highly valued program

component during their implementation of a Healthy Lifestyle program. One of the teaching strategies in this project will include performing the CAM-ICU screening at bedside with the project lead observing and serving as backup to support learning (bedside application). Face to face instruction will thus occur at bedside, so that learners' questions can be answered and immediate feedback given, facilitating skilled practice and understanding of the tool.

In a review, Yanamadala, Wieland, and Heflin (2013) mentioned that the project leader should visit ICU wards daily to identify problems related to performance and adherence to CAM-ICU and provide personal or group feedback. They also supported/found that champions helped with outcomes of the implementation. Studies from this review identified the key role of the nurse champions in bridging the gap between research and practice; for example, nurse champions were able to help others improve the recognition of delirium in the critical care setting. One of the objectives for this project is to develop nurse champions who will play a key role in bridging the gap between new knowledge and application at bedside. Bradshaw and Lowenstein (2011) found that having the opportunity to discuss clinical care experiences with their peers was helpful to nurses in validating decisions and gaining further insights. Boud, Cohen, and Sampson (2014) essentially identified the importance of "peer learning" and how learners improved their skills by participating in activities and explaining their ideas to others. Nurse champions play an important role in the sustainability of the program. Nurse champions, being peers, will be available to help nurses answer questions during the use of the tool.

Adult Learning Theory and Teaching Strategies

An objective of the educational program is to teach nurses how to effectively utilize the CAM-ICU tool in identifying delirium. To achieve this, there were four elements identified as valuable for successful implementation of the program. One of the elements is the development of self-learning module (SLM) to address delirium and use of CAM-ICU. Based on informal interviews of nurses in the unit, one of the challenges identified with the CAM-ICU tool was its complexity. Understanding how nurses acquire new knowledge is the first step in the successful re-implementation of this tool. According to Knowles, Holton, and Swanson (2014), adult learners tend to be self-directed, but also task and goal oriented. Therefore, it is important to tailor the learning strategies so that nurses are able to appreciate the purpose of the tool. Learning experiences should allow for repetition of tasks under a variety of situations (Knowles, Holton, & Swanson, 2014).

Self-learning Module

A self-learning module (SLM) is a flexible way of teaching that enhances not only nurses' knowledge and skills but also the unit's educational program (Clifford, Goldschmidt, & O'Connor, 2006). It allows for flexibility and accommodation of diverse backgrounds, learning skills and busy nursing schedules. The SLM is convenient for nurses working any shift. In a prospective study, Gagnon et al. (2015) found significant improvement in knowledge and skills of nurses using a SLM for learning critical appraisal skills, as well as satisfaction of nurses using the module.

However, not all learning objectives can be met with SLM. For SLM to be effective, aims must be narrow and specific. Topics that are presented repeatedly and

remain consistent over time are appropriate for SLM (Schmidt & Fisher, 2017). The tasks for developing SLM are: (a) determining the need for the module; (b) developing learning objectives; (c) determining if the SLM technique is appropriate for topic and for learners; (d) developing content; (e) establishing format (introduction, pretest, feedback mechanisms, posttest, artwork); (f) pilot testing; (g) evaluating learning (Schmidt & Fisher, 2017). Furthermore, in a systematic review of 59 studies with 8011 health care professional as learners, Murad, Coto-Yglesias, Varkey, Prokop, and Murad (2010) found that in health professions education, SLM was moderately associated with improvement in knowledge, skills and attitudes-based outcomes. In this project, the gap in unit nurse knowledge provided the focus in outlining the objectives for the self-learning module. The content of the SLM included topics that will address delirium and identifying the negative outcomes if CAM-ICU tool is not used appropriately. The SLM included content about different nursing interventions to identify delirium.

Teaching Strategies

According to Kenner and Weinerman (2011), adult learners should be regarded as individuals who have different learning styles. Based on Kolb's learning theory, that different people naturally prefer a certain single different learning style, the educational program was developed with different elements to address the four basic learning styles:

1. **Convergers:** Prefer to think about things and then try out their ideas to see if they work in practice. They like to ask 'how' about . . . Convergers seem to do best with problems or situations that require a single correct answer.

2. Divergers: Learn best by interacting and discussing. Divergers are interested in people and tend to be emotional and imaginative. They are sometimes called “idea people.” They do best by listening and talking to others.
3. Assimilators: Prefer to think than to act. They ask ‘What is there I can know?’ and like organized and structured understanding. They prefer lectures for learning.
4. Accommodators: People with this learning style are strongest in concrete experience. They enjoy performing experiments and carrying out plans in the real world.

The program consisted of a self-learning module, pre- and post-test, feedback, bedside application, use of nurse champions, resource materials such as laminated CAM-ICU tool and unit resource binder, and competency checklist. These elements will address the different learning styles of nurses and bridge the gap of knowledge identified by the nurses. Once the project lead begins to work one-on-one with nurses to help fine tune their skills in using the tool, instruction will become individualized. Each learner will be treated according to her or his level of knowledge, background and values. Bradshaw and Lowenstein (2011) strongly suggested that the best way to bring about effective learning is by recognizing students as individuals, with unique personal ways of knowing and learning, by creating learning situations that recognize diversity, and by providing experiences that empower students to challenge their thinking.

In this project setting, nurses have reported that they find the tool complex to use. Squires et al. (2014) supported the idea of using single or less complex multifaceted interventions for changing healthcare professionals’ behavior in clinical settings. This is

relevant since the primary purpose of the QI project is to develop and implement an educational program to re-educate the nurses. The educational program includes multiple teaching strategies which are supported by evidence to have succeeded in changing providers' behavior (Squires et al., 2014). By understanding the nurses and taking into consideration individual background and experiences, re-introduction of the CAM-ICU tool will be done using learning experiences that meet different learning styles. Face to face instruction was the most highly valued program components during the program implementation by Kozica et al. (2012). Use of the tool will be explained in simple words that nurses can understand. Nurses will be encouraged to ask questions and project lead/nurse champions will clarify and address nurses' concerns. It is recommended that feedback be provided through evaluations and oral communication in order to assess learning of the recipients (Talmage, Lacher, Pstross, Knopf, & Burkhart, 2015). Feedback will be given to nurses at bedside during assessments with actual patient using of the tool.

Scaffolding

Scaffolding refers to a variety of teaching strategies used to move students progressively toward a stronger understanding and, ultimately, greater independence in the use of the tool and learning. Scaffolding is a way to assist learners with attaining a level of understanding by building on prior knowledge when introducing new content (Alias, 2012). Scaffolding improves motivation and sustainment of learning. Alber (2011) identified six scaffolding strategies to help develop learners' competency: show and tell, tap into prior knowledge, give time to talk, pre-teach vocabulary, use visual aids, pause, ask questions, pause, and review. Scaffolding was used in each area of the

program; for example, during the face-to-face bedside application, nurses will be given time to talk and the project lead or champion will use pausing and asking questions as well as tapping into prior knowledge. It was also applied during the development of the SLM by introducing the topic of delirium and CAM-ICU in a more simplified way for nurses to understand.

Lauerer, Edlund, Williams, Donato, and Smith (2017) described the use of scaffolding by slowly integrating a behavioral health assessment and interventions into primary care curriculum for nurse practitioners (NP). Their results showed improvement in NP competence to identify, manage and treat common behavioral health care problems. The methods used in the study were combining online learning cases with on campus learning to assist NPs in understanding behavioral health disorders. Alias (2012) found that scaffolding techniques such as using feedback mechanisms supported the sustainability of students' motivation to use on-line self-learning modules. In this QI project,

The SLM will provide the basic content of the scaffolding process. The knowledge learned from the SLM is needed for nurses to assess patients, utilize the tool effectively, and provide evidence-based interventions. Verbal feedback from the learners during bedside assessment will initiate discussion and collaboration and allow clarification of any understanding problems. Bedside application of the CAM-ICU provides experiential use of the tool with the project lead or nurse champions as resources. This experience should prepare the nurses to apply their skill to real patients.

Schmidt and Fisher (1992) identified videotape and print materials as some of the ways to assist nurse educators in developing scaffolding techniques for learners. In this project, the SLM included video clips from a patient survivor and another video on how nurses use the tool in assessing the patient. Once the topic is broken into smaller pieces, use of video clips or images allows students to more fully understand delirium.

Nursing Practice Champions

Some learners respond better to challenges during complex situations (Fabricatore & Lopez, 2014). In a review on delirium screening tools in adult and pediatric ICUs (Brummel et al., 2013), education led by nurse “champions” to implement a delirium screening using the CAM-ICU tool resulted in a compliance increase from 85% to more than 90%. Similarly, Soja et al. (2008) studied CAM-ICU training with nurse champions, nurse educators, and bedside education regarding the tool and found nurses completed the CAM-ICU assessments in 84% (849 of 1011) of evaluations. Carrothers et al. (2013) found that implementation of delirium screening was enhanced with support from nurse champions. Furthermore, Balas et al. (2013) used staff volunteers as champions in the successfully implemented Awakening and Breathing Coordination, Choice of drugs, Delirium monitoring and management, Early mobility (ABCDE) Bundle. One of the elements of the educational program being developed for this project is identifying five nurse champions for ICU. The 20% of nurses who understood and were competent in the use of the tool would be good nurse champions for this DNP project; however, volunteers will be sought so it is not guaranteed that these “best case” nurses will volunteer. After being checked-off by the project lead, the nurse champions will serve as resources for the other 73 staff nurses in Critical Care. Along with the

project lead, they will be responsible for providing training, and check-off competencies during nurses' application of assessment at bedside.

Glanz et al. (2015) found that program champions helped with the sustainability of a program on skin cancer prevention. One of the strategies for this QI project is to develop champions for the implementation of the CAM-ICU tool. This will help during the program implementation and sustainability as these champions will have varied work schedules and thus, will increase availability of support than if the project leader were the sole facilitator.

Educational Assessment

The role of assessment and evaluation is important in an educational program. Educational assessment has two components in this project: the nurses and the educational program.

Learner Evaluation

Evaluation is an interactive process between recipients and providers of innovation that informs whether learning occurs. Evaluation has two components, formative and summative evaluation.

Learner Formative Assessment. This is done during a learning experience so that the educator can get feedback on how well the learning is going, and change the strategies if needed. The posttest from the SLM, and nurses' verbal feedback during the bedside application are the formative assessments included in this project.

Learner Summative Assessment. The summative assessment identifies whether the learner understands and is able to effectively use the information in practice. These

are the scores from the post-test and the competency skills checklist developed by the project lead. This assessment is performed to obtain a final evaluation of how much learning has taken place – that is, a nurse should be able to appropriately screen a patient for delirium using the CAM-ICU tool and address the nursing interventions needed for the patient.

Program Evaluation

There are two kinds of program evaluation: formative and summative. Program evaluation is the process of making judgements regarding the interventions of the program (Madaus, Scriven & Stufflebeam, 2012) to determine if the program is effective. Educational programs consist of groups of independent learning activities to meet projected outcomes.

Formative program assessment. To evaluate the program during implementation, focus needs to be on the process. It is a method for judging the worth of a program while program activities are in progress. During implementation of the educational program, formative assessment will allow the project lead to determine how nurses are doing during the program. It also helps to determine how the nurses are effectively using the tool in the screening of delirium. Formative assessment of the program will be the assessment of nurses' answers to the SLM to determine level of understanding of the material: did the nurses learn the material given to them in the SLM? The on-going communication between project lead and nurse champions with nurses for feedback during the implementation of this project is also part of the formative assessment.

Summative program assessment. This evaluation refers to the assessment of the program outcomes. Summative assessment will determine if the program is effective in getting nurses to appropriately screen patients for delirium using the CAM-ICU, document their findings, and use appropriate nursing interventions. The program assessment will determine if the objectives set were met or not. Once nurses are trained, monthly chart audits (Appendix L) will determine if they perform accurate and timely screening of delirium using the tool. If not, further assessment will be used to determine barriers to effective delirium assessment and care. The identification of one individual to be responsible for the overall evaluation aids this process (McLeod et al., 1994). In this project, this individual will be the project lead.

Competency Evaluation

Competence was defined by Fernandez et al. (2012) as the ability to perform the task well as manifested by the learners' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. Competency will be evaluated based on the nurse's ability to accurately identify delirium using the CAM-ICU tool. Competency assessment will help nurses understand that they can learn from their experiences. This helps with learner motivation and develops confidence and commitment to learning.

To have an effective framework in assessing the performance and competencies of the learners, a Competency Assessment Checklist (Appendix K) was developed utilizing three of the eight core practice competencies from Competency Outcomes and Performance Assessment (COPA) Model (Lenberg, Badura-Rahman, Spencer, Boyer & Klein, 2011). Competency elements such as assessment, teaching skills, and knowledge integration skills were addressed during the development of the competency checklist.

The nurses will be assessed for their performance at bedside and are expected to demonstrate knowledge learned from the SLM. In this QI project, this competency assessment will be done initially during the bedside assessment of the patient using the tool with the project lead or the nurse champion as resource.

Summary

In summary, delirium is an acute state of mind that occurs among ICU patients. It is associated with increased hospital stay, mortality and functional disability after discharge. Without the use of a reliable and valid screening tool, delirium may not be recognized and treated, which negatively affects patient safety. The re-introduction of the use of the CAM-ICU tool, when properly administered, should assist nurses at bedside in identifying and recognizing delirium before it becomes severe. Once diagnosed, treatment can begin according to existing unit guidelines.

The development of an educational program, a self-learning module, pre- and post-test, bedside application, nurse champions as facilitators, and evaluation using a competency checklist will address issues identified by project site nurses. Evidence-based teaching strategies such as the use of scaffolding, feedback, peer learning and a laminated pocket-sized CAM-ICU tool which serves as a reference and learning guide for nurses, should lead to improvement in the knowledge and competency acquisition and sustainability.

As part of understanding how adult learners adopt new knowledge, the background knowledge of every learner needs to be considered. Evidence supported student-centered instruction where students are given opportunities to be active participants in the construction of knowledge. Interactive discussions during bedside

application provides learners with a sense of ownership in the experience and creates a safe space to ask questions and refine learning. Feedback is one way of clarifying whether the goals and objectives on learning how to use the CAM-ICU tool, were met or not. Evidence suggests the importance of nurse champions in the sustainability of program outcomes.

METHODS

This QI project was designed to address improper use of the CAM-ICU tool for delirium screening in a critical care unit through the development and use of an educational program for nurses. During an early review of patient records (2015), it was determined that nurses were not accurately using their assessments and screening tools. Informal interviews determined the areas that could be addressed through formal training and re-education of nurses on CAM-ICU usage. Four project aims helped to focus program development. The total package of education should facilitate accurate use of the tool at bedside.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to commencement of this project, a chart review of patient records and informal interviews were conducted. Documentation of nurse assessments related to delirium were reviewed using the Electronic Medical Record system. This component of the project was approved by the ICU manager. During the chart review, patient records were examined for evidence of implementation/use of the tool and accurate assessment of delirium. No identifying information was used in reports generated.

In the summer of 2017, the project proposal was submitted for review to the Institutional Review Board of the project hospital system and it was determined that as QI, the project did not require formal review (Appendix B).

Setting

The QI project was developed for a 26-bed ICU, in a faith-based, non-profit hospital located in Orange County. The hospital has 320-beds with over 200 healthcare providers working on site. The hospital specializes in breast care, cancer, cardiac, maternity, orthopedics, rehabilitation and neurosciences/stroke. The ICU has patients with various medical conditions who require continuous monitoring. Per the Critical Care Unit Standard of Care, delirium screening using the CAM-ICU is required once per shift on all patients, and as needed.

Recipients

The recipients are the 73 staff nurses who work on the ICU unit. Nurses range in age from 25 to 72 and have a work history ranging from new graduates to experienced nurses with more than 30 years' experience. Educational levels range from associate degree to doctorate.

Phases of the Project

The goal of this project was the development of an educational program. The aim of the program was to re-educate the nurses in the use of the CAM-ICU tool in a manner that is understandable and applicable at bedside. Developing effective educational programs requires the facilitator to understand the recipients' learning styles (Kitson and Harvey, 2016). Teaching strategies planned to enable successful implementation of CAM-ICU are a self-learning module, use of content experts and nurse champions, and evaluation using knowledge assessment, and competency checklist, and one-to-one work with nurses at the bedside.

For this project, the i-PARIHS model (Kitson & Harvey, 2016) was adapted in the development of the educational program. Each of the five aspects of the framework: innovation, recipients, inner context: local, inner context: organization, and outer context were considered during the formulation of the project. Objectives for the program were formulated based on what critical care nurses need to understand to use CAM-ICU.

The educational program consists of a self-learning module, pre- and post-test for the module, bedside application, strategies for developing nurse champions, unit resources (laminated CAM-ICU tool and resource manual), and competency checklist. Bedside application is designed as an interactive process wherein the project lead or nurse champion provides guidance to nurse learners. Nurses will receive feedback after each instructional element. There will be no intimidation or fault-finding comments during verbal feedback. Practice sessions using the tool at the bedside were included in the educational program. A competency checklist was developed to evaluate application of knowledge.

Development of Online Self-learning Module (SLM) with Pre/Post tests

The SLM contains 43 slides with pre- and post-test. Content depicts systematically organized content on delirium and CAM-ICU tool. The following represent steps taken by the project lead in order to complete the SLM.

Based on the results from the informal interview conducted with ICU nurses (12/1/16), the initial need assessment focused on the statement of nurses not understanding what delirium is, and that the CAM-ICU was complicated and time-consuming. Random chart audits were performed on 10 patients, with main focus on nurses' assessment on delirium using the CAM-ICU (1/1/17). From the audit, the project

lead identified inconsistent assessment from nurses. She then met with the ICU manager, ICU director and CNS to report results from the informal interview and chart audit (2/1/17). These individuals have knowledge, skills and interest in the outcome of the project, which will be of benefit when attempting full implementation of the project. They are considered to be valuable members and supporters for the SLM. The CNS reviewed the information as a content expert.

The meeting with the ICU manager, director, and CNS concluded that the unit needed an educational program with the overall objective of retraining nurses to successfully use the CAM-ICU tool to assess for delirium and provide appropriate care for patients with delirium. Results from literature search provided the evidence and were used as basis in the development of the SLM (5/1/17 to 12/1/17). The project lead met with content expert (CNS) and finalized what was to be included in the SLM during Fall 2017. She then formulated four objectives for SLM to address nurse knowledge gaps and problems identified with using the CAM-ICU: (1) Identify the key features of delirium in adults; (2) Identify the three types of delirium; (3) List the effects of unrecognized delirium in ICU; (4) Differentiate the four features of the CAM-ICU tool.

A content outline for the SLM was created Fall 2017 (Appendix D). The content of each section of the SLM was determined based on the learning objectives.

The project lead determined video clips that could be adapted from the ICU Delirium website and then included in the SLM (Fall 2017). The video clips were found on the website's comprehensive resources page. This website is an educational website provided by Vanderbilt University Medical Center (VUMC). The website's learning video showcased Dr. Wes Ely, ICU physician from VUMC, well known for research

studies on CAM-ICU and delirium. Permission was obtained to use the videos (Appendix C).

The content of the SLM (Appendix D) was developed under the direction and guidance of a nursing instructor who has expertise and experience with instructional design. Initially, 20 power point slides were created; 43 slides resulted from the multiple reviews from the instructional designer. The project lead reviewed and revised the content of the SLM to create a smooth flow of ideas. The instructional designer approved the final product by (12/9/17). The project lead determined that it takes about 30 minutes to go through the slides (12/10/17). The content expert provided a final evaluation and approved the SLM content (12/11/17). She also approved the pre- and post-test (2/7/18).

The approved SLM (Appendix E) includes information about delirium, the three types of delirium, and problems associated with untreated delirium. A video narrated by an ICU patient who experienced delirium and his wife; discusses their experiences of hallucinations, false ideas, or paranoia. This video shows the significant impact of delirium on family and caregivers, and the difficulty for loved ones to understand. Watching this video may help nurses understand the experiences of some patients. The SLM also has a “how-to” video that illustrates a nurse screening a patient using the CAM-ICU and documenting the results. Two slides from the SLM provide examples of nursing interventions to address delirium: (1) assess, prevent, and manage pain; (2) coordinate with respiratory therapist for faster liberation from mechanical ventilation; (3) targeted lighter sedation when sedation is necessary; (4) non-pharmacologic intervention, including sleep hygiene; (5) early mobility and exercise; (6) family engagement and

empowerment. The slides were organized in such a way that the integrated pathophysiology of delirium with applied content in a comprehensive and simple way.

Plan for Implementation

The SLM will be assigned to nurses over a two-week period during Summer 2018. It will be given to the education liaison for posting in Health Stream, the educational portal of the project site. The 10 questions on the pre- and post-test assess key concepts of the SLM's objectives (Appendix F) and were embedded in the SLM. Nine of the questions are multiple choice, and one is true or false. The pretest is given before the nurse starts the SLM. After the nurse completes the SLM, the posttest is given.

A passing score of 80% is required to show adequate knowledge. The education department liaison will set up the tests in the Health Stream module to allow nurses to take the post-test up to three times. The education liaison will send the list of the nurses who failed to the project lead and nurse manager. If a nurse fails to pass on the third testing, she/he will be required to meet with the ICU manager.

Development and Use of Competency Checklist

A competency checklist was developed by the project lead as a standard to evaluate whether nurses are able to correctly use the CAM-ICU tool and enable her or a nurse champion to appropriately intervene if indicated during the bedside application (Appendix K). The items on the checklist come from the steps of CAM_ICU administration and help determine if the nurse can identify the four features of delirium.

The checklist was presented during Fall 2017 to the project site CNS and was approved February, 2018. Initially, the checklist will be used by the project lead to check

off the skills of the five nurse champions. A passing score of 80% on the SLM and 19 of 21 items from the checklist must be completed accurately to achieve competency. There are no critical points that would cause failure but nurses are expected to obtain 90-100%.

The project lead will evaluate the nurse champions' bedside application and use of the tool based on the competency checklist. The evaluation of their competency will occur after they completed and passed the SLM and their assessment of a real patient will happen at bedside. Each nurse champion will have a competency assessment for at least three patients with different diagnosis and presenting symptoms.

Once the education department liaison provides the staff nurse scores from the SLM to the project lead, she will schedule nurses for the bedside application portion of the educational program. Successful completion of the competency checklist in the presence of the project lead or a nurse champion will be required of newly hired nurses in addition to use by the nurse champions in evaluating current nursing staff on the unit.

If the nurse does not pass, another chance to complete the competency will be provided. If not successfully completed after three attempts, the unit manager will be informed. Once successful, all nurses will be re-evaluated during the annual skills lab set by the hospital (October). The annual competency and orientation of new hire nurses to use the CAM-ICU will be conducted by the project lead and five nurse champions.

The CAM-ICU resource manual will be available for nurses to use in the unit. It will be kept in a place as where all other resources were kept.

Plan for Program Implementation

Pilot with Five Nurses

The educational program (SLM and bedside assessment) will be piloted on five nurses from the project unit (two from morning shift and three from the night shift). The five nurses will be selected according to their availability and willingness to serve. Volunteers will be preferred, a combination of novice and experienced nurses will be valuable. After they complete the SLM and pass the post-test (80%), post-test scores will be compared to pretest scores. Individual discussion with each nurse will provide feedback and evaluation of the module. Each nurse will experience the bedside assessment where they will assess and evaluate a real patient using the CAM-ICU (Appendix K). The project lead will do the competency assessment at this time. After this experience, face to face discussion with the project lead will occur to allow further feedback and questions.

Nurse Champions

The QI project will be presented at the unit's monthly staff meeting by summer of 2018. The nurse champions and their responsibilities will be explained. How will they be selected if > 5 volunteer? What if the shift breakdown is not as you want (above)? Once selected and trained, Frequent communications with the nurse champions by email or text messaging with the project lead will be encouraged to assure success of program objectives. Quarterly meetings with the nurse champions will be scheduled to discuss issues and trends of the program.

The selected nurse champions will complete the SLM. Results from the SLM post-test will be provided by the education liaison to the project lead then those nurse

champions who passed the test will be evaluated for bedside application of CAM-ICU. This is when the nurse champions would do the competency assessments on 3 patients. The project lead will coordinate and assign each nurse champion with 12 nurses to evaluate their competency using the checklist. These competency assessments will occur during the nurses' work time and only when their assigned patient conditions are stable and acuity is low.

Plan for Evaluation

After the educational program has been implemented, and all critical care nurses have passed the competency, future assessment will be conducted by the project lead to determine whether critical care patients are being appropriately screened for delirium and nursing interventions followed. The project lead developed a program evaluation rounding tool (Appendix L) to screen 10 patients (48 hours each) to cover both day/night shift. The project lead will collaborate with the Information Technology (IT) department to extract data from the electronic record. The following questions will be answered with the audit results:

1. Did the nurse screen the patient using CAM-ICU and document the results?
(Yes/No)
2. At each data point, was the patient screened positive or negative?
3. Was the nursing plan of care changed related to positive screening? (Yes/No)

The plan for evaluation of this project will include determining whether the program objectives were met, and will provide a basis for identifying strengths and concerns for the various strategies used in this project. One component of the evaluation is the assessment of the nurses' ability to use the tool in recognizing delirium. Modifications

and updates of the program will be planned to make sure that the program remains current, and provides evidence based knowledge.

DISCUSSION

The successful implementation of an educational program depends on many factors. Based on the iPARIHS theoretical framework, the five aspects, which include the innovation, recipients, inner context: local, inner context: organization and outer context should be considered in the formulation of objectives and elements for the educational program. The framework was helpful to the project lead as it indicated how innovation such as the re-introduction of CAM-ICU could be implemented successfully. It is necessary for the nurses to understand the importance of the innovation for them to accept a change in practice. The framework provided better understanding of the nurses, as learners, and the advantage of the support from the management and organization where the project will be implemented.

The literature reviewed provided evidence and strategies which helped me accomplish this project. Systematic reviews and individual studies strongly indicated that the successful completion of the self-learning module will optimize the knowledge base of the nurses. The bedside application will allow transfer of this knowledge to bedside. Support from the project hospital's manager, CNS and nurse champions will promote sustainability of the program.

Kolb's experiential learning theory indicated that for learning to take place, nurses should be actually doing the activity. The educational program includes bedside application of using the tool in assessing patient's delirium. Here the main emphasis is directed to the nurses; this allows for their active participation in using the CAM-ICU with feedback from an observer. The program includes a variety of evidence-based

teaching strategies to facilitate successful learning. It is designed to meet the needs of different types of learners.

During the implementation of the program, the project lead and five nurse champions will be providing support and served as a resource for the nurses. How the nurses respond to new knowledge will depend on their values, motivation, beliefs, knowledge, skills, and time. Nurses should be given the chance to understand the value of learning this skill. Making nurses understand the importance of recognizing delirium, especially subtle states, and the use of a reliable tool, will help nurses make appropriate intervention decisions.

Four elements of the educational program are self-learning modules, bedside application, use of champions, and competency checklist tend to increase knowledge, skills, confidence and satisfaction of the nurses. Research strongly suggested the use of multiple strategies such as feedback, peer learning, face-to-face instruction, and resource manual to address different levels of learners.

It is equally important to develop assessment tools for learning, competency and program development in order to evaluate transfer of skills and determine if learning has occurred. The learning and program assessment will guide the project lead to retrain as needed, which will improve the program and will be based on feedback of the learners and performance.

There were several things learned from doing this project. Developing an educational program is an extensive effort and requires scientific underpinnings for practice. The elements of the program (e.g., SLM and competency checklist) were supported by systematic reviews and individual studies and should be successful in

facilitating learning about delirium and use of the CAM-ICU. Having known how adult learners accept innovation through recognition of supporting theories from Kolb and the i-PARIHS framework, the development of an educational program has to be learner-focused. For the project to be implemented in the project site, organizational and systems leadership buy-ins were also important. The support from the unit manager and CNS are examples of the organizational context identified by Kitson and Harvey (2016).

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APPENDIX A

STEP 1 RICHMOND AGITATION-SEDATION SCALE (RASS)		
Sedation Assessment		
Scale	Label	Description
+4	COMBATIVE	Combative, violent, immediate danger to staff
+3	VERY AGITATED	Pulls to remove tubes or catheters; aggressive
+2	AGITATED	Frequent non-purposeful movement, fights ventilator
+1	RESTLESS	Anxious, apprehensive, movements not aggressive
0	ALERT & CALM	Spontaneously pays attention to caregiver
-1	DROWSY	Not fully alert, but has sustained awakening to voice (eye opening & contact >10 sec)
-2	LIGHT SEDATION	Briefly awakens to voice (eyes open & contact <10 sec)
<p>If RASS is = -2 proceed to CAM-ICU (is patient CAM-ICU positive or negative?)</p>		
-3	MODERATE SEDATION	Movement or eye opening to voice (no eye contact)
-4	DEEP SEDATION	No response to voice, but movement or eye opening to physical stimulation
-5	UNAROUSEABLE	No response to voice or physical stimulation
<p>If RASS is -3, -4 or -5 → STOP (patient unconscious), RECHECK later</p>		

Sessler, et al., Am J Respir Crit Care Med 2002; 166: 1338-1344

Ely, et al., JAMA 2003; 285: 2983-2991

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APPENDIX B

CERTIFICATE OF HRPP DETERMINATION

July 25, 2017

Project Title: Enhancing Screening and Management of Delirium in Critical Care

Dear Ms. Zenaida Co:

This is to advise you that the above referenced project has been presented to the St. Joseph Health System Human Research Protection Program (HRPP) Office for review, and the following action was taken with the explanation provided below:

Determination:

- The project does not meet the definition of research
- The project does not meet the definition of human subjects
- The site is not engaged in Human Subjects Research according to OHRP "Engagement of Institutions in Human Subjects Research (2008)"

Rationale: The SJH HRPP Office reviewed the above-referenced submission and determined that the project does not require SJH IRB Oversight under 45 CFR 46, 21 CFR 56, and SJH Policy due to the following:

- Project does not involve a systematic investigation designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge.
- The project does not involve a living individual about whom an investigator conducting research obtains: (1) data through intervention or interaction with the individual or (2) identifiable private information.

3345 Michelson Drive, Suite 100 • Irvine, CA 92612
T: (949) 381-4907 • F: (949) 381-4984

A Ministry founded by the Sisters of St. Joseph of Orange

APPENDIX C

Permission to Use Video from Leicester's Hospital

 Communications <communications@uhl-tr.nhs.uk>
Today, 3:48 AM
Co, Zenaida

Hi Zenaida,

We are happy for you to use this. Please could you reference Leicester's Hospitals if possible.

Many thanks,

Kim Salt
Communications Officer
University Hospitals of Leicester NHS Trust
0116 258 8644
07950 881 532

 Co, Zenaida
Yesterday, 9:13 PM

To whom it may concern,

My name is Zenaida Co, I am currently enrolled in a Doctoral program for Nursing Practice at California State University of Fullerton. As part of my project, I would like to ask permission to use one of your videos in my self-learning module created for the Critical Care nurses. My project is on "Enhancing screening and management of delirium in Critical care" and the specific video I would like to use is:

Delirium: A Patient Story at Leicester's Hospitals

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9G3yJNOGCok>

Permission to Use Video from Peace health

 Reply
 Yesterday, 8:50 AM
 Co, Zenaida; DLPHO-Public Affairs <DLPHOPublicAffairs@peacehealth.org>

Zenaida, I tracked down the creator of the video and she's totally OK with you using it. Good luck with your doctoral program!

Anne Williams | Senior Communications Specialist | Communications & Marketing
PeaceHealth | [770 E. 11th Avenue | Eugene, OR 97401](#)
office 541-686-6857 | **mobile** 541-554-9403
 ...

 Thank you Anne! Zenaida K. Co, MSN, RN, CCRN, CMC, CSC Part-Time Faculty – Clinical Instructor Cal State Fullerton | School of Nursing T 657-278-3336... Sun 3/18

 Williams, Anne <AWilliams5@peacehealth.org> Hello Zenaida, Thanks for very much for checking with us on this. I've reached out to our Clinical Education team to see if this would be OK. I'll let you know... Thu 3/7

To whom it may concern,

My name is Zenaida Co, I am currently enrolled in a Doctoral program for Nursing Practice at California State University of Fullerton. As part of my project, I would like to ask permission to use one of your videos in my self-learning module created for the Critical Care nurses. My project is on "Enhancing screening and management of delirium in Critical care" and the specific video I would like to use is:

CAM ICU Assessment
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lvJNz55VQZE>

Permission to Use Video from www.icudelirium.org

Williams, Angie <angie.williams@vumc.org>

Today, 9:56 AM

Zenaida, I spoke with Dr. Ely this morning and you are approved to use the videos on our website at www.icudelirium.org . Please be sure to acknowledge and include the copyright information. Good luck with your project.

Committed to serving,

Angie Williams
Administrative Assistant for
Wes Ely, MD, MPH
Phone: 615-936-3395
Fax: 615-936-1269
angie.williams@vanderbilt.edu
www.icudelirium.org
...

Co, Zenaida

Yesterday, 1:56 PM

angie.williams@vanderbilt.edu

To whom it may concern,

My name is Zenaida Co, I am currently enrolled in a Doctoral program for Nursing Practice at California State University of Fullerton. As part of my project, I would like to ask permission to use three of your videos posted in your website at icudelirium.org in my self-learning module created for the Critical Care nurses. My project is on "Enhancing screening and management of delirium in Critical care".

Thank you very much.

Hope to hear from you soon.

Sincerely yours,

APPENDIX D

Content Outline for the Self Learning Module

- I. Educational Program and Elements
 - A. Program Objective
 - B. Elements of the Program
- II. Delirium Module
 - A. SLM objectives
 1. What is delirium?
 - a) Video clip narration of a patient
 - b) Delirium in ICU
 - c) What causes delirium
 - d) Why is it important to assess delirium?
 - e) Summary
 2. Risk factors for delirium
 3. Four features of delirium
 - a) How to identify four features of delirium
 4. Three types of delirium
- III. What is CAM-ICU tool?
 - A. How do I use the tool?
 - B. Video clip on step by step process of using the tool
 - C. Video clip on a nurse assessing a patient at bedside using the tool
- IV. Documentation
- V. Bedside Management and Prevention of Delirium

APPENDIX E

This is a video of a patient who experienced delirium while in ICU.

This can help health care personnel understand what it's like to have delirium.

Click video to play

L. (2017, June 15). Retrieved September 09, 2017, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9563jP50G0k>

why is it important to assess delirium?

- ▶ Delirium can develop relatively quickly (usually over hours to days) and tends to fluctuate during the course of the day (Inouye, 2006).
- ▶ Without screening, greater than 66% of patients with delirium may go undiagnosed (Inouye, 2006).
- ▶ Inaccurate and untimely assessment of delirium among ICU patients contributes to prolonged hospital stays, increase in complications, unnecessary hospital costs, and increased mortality and morbidity rates (Garcia-Flores et al., 2012).

Delirium in ICU

Delirium is a disturbance of consciousness that includes 4 features:

- * change in cognition
- * inattention
- * altered level of consciousness
- * disorganized thinking

American Psychiatric Association, 1994

why is it important to assess delirium?

- ▶ Long term cognitive impairment is 10-fold higher at discharge if delirium is not recognized and treated (Garcia-Flores et al., 2012).
- ▶ Delirium increases risk of mortality by 62% (Meymann et al., 2010).
- ▶ Total cost estimates attributable to delirium is \$64,421 per patient (Lofth et al., 2011).
- ▶ Total annual costs nationally to treat delirium is \$145-\$152 billion (Lofth et al., 2011).

What causes delirium?

Drugs (e.g., sedatives, or withdrawal from smoking or alcohol)

Use of restraints and catheters

Abnormal Laboratory Values

Infection (e.g., sepsis, UTI, or respiratory infections)

Sleep and sensory deprivation (poor vision, and hearing)

Weyman et al., 2010

In summary.....

- ▶ Delirium is an acute state of mind.
- ▶ Delirium is often unrecognized.
- ▶ Delirium has serious complications.
- ▶ Delirium is expensive.
- ▶ Using a valid and reliable tool, improves detection of delirium.

What are the risk factors for delirium?

How to identify four features of delirium

Feature 1 – refers to Level of Cognition

Delirium patients have acute changes in their level of cognition. To determine if changes are present, ask yourself:

Is the patient's mental status different from baseline mental status?

Has there been any fluctuation in mental status in last 24 hours?

Mayhew et al., 2011

Mnemonic for risk factors and causes of delirium:
ICI: Delirium(s)

- ▶ **I**ntoxigen exposure (eg, dopamine precursors)
- ▶ **C**ognitive impairment (pre-existing dementia, or depression)
- ▶ **I**nsulin and antibiotics
- ▶ **I**nsulin (eg, infection, or withdrawal from smoking or alcohol)
- ▶ **E**lderly (old or older)
- ▶ **L**aboratory abnormalities
- ▶ **I**nfection (eg, sepsis, UTI, or respiratory infection)
- ▶ **R**espiratory (PDD>4 usually or PDD>5 usually, COPD, ARDS, PE)
- ▶ **T**reatment problems (HTN, hypotension, blood clots, stroke, sepsis)
- ▶ **U**riinary fluid retention
- ▶ **M**etabolic (ME, acute liver failure, acylglutathione)
- ▶ **S**leep and sensory deprivation (poor vision, and hearing)

Dy et al., 2001

How to Identify four features of delirium

Feature 2 – refers to Inattention

To determine the presence of Inattention, instruct the patient to squeeze your hand when you say the letter A.

Then spell out "SQUEAZEAART."

The number of times the patient misses to squeeze the hand when letter A is said determines the Attention Screening Exam (ASE) Letters Score.

Mayhew et al., 2011

To distinguish delirium from other types of cognitive impairment.....

There are four features:

- ▶ Level of cognition
- ▶ Inattention
- ▶ Altered level of consciousness
- ▶ Disorganized thinking

How to Identify four features of delirium

Feature 2 – refers to Inattention

Use the ASE: Pictures if the patient is unable to perform the assessment using the ASE Letters Score.

Show patient pictures of five objects such as table, chair, etc.

Pause for few minutes then come back to show same pictures of the objects with additional pictures of different objects.

Ask patient if she remembers seeing these objects from the previous time.

Inattention is present if score for either ASE Letters or ASE Pictures is < 2

Mayhew et al., 2011

Laminated ASE pictures are in the drawers of each patient's room in ICU

Why do you think each patient manifests delirium differently?

When caring for patients with delirium, have you ever noticed each patient manifested the delirium differently?

That is because, in addition to the common features or characteristics of delirium, there are three types of delirium.

How to Identify four features of delirium

Feature 3 – refers to Altered Level of Consciousness (ALOC)

- Determining the RASS Score will give you Feature 3
- ALOC is absent if the most current score of RASS is (0), or Alert and Calm

Mogho W. d., 2011

Types of delirium

- ▶ **Hyperactive ("Wild person")**
 - ▶ Hyperactive delirium is what people typically think of when discussing delirium.
 - ▶ Patient is extremely agitated and emotionally labile
 - ▶ Characteristic: agitated, combative, uncooperative, or aggressive behavior; hallucinations; disorientation; pulling at lines, tubes, and equipment

Nasirideen A. Thomas, 2011

How to identify the 4 features of delirium

Feature 4 – refers to Disorganized Thinking
Complete Feature 4 only if Feature 3 is absent

Ask "Yes/No" Questions:
Are there fish in the sea?
Is one pound heavier than two pounds?
Can a hammer float in water?

Determine if patient is able to follow commands:
"Yes/No"

Disorganized Thinking is present if there is "1" answer for the combined "Yes/No" Questions and Commands

Mogho W. d., 2011

Types of Delirium

- ▶ **Hypoactive ("out of it")**
 - ▶ Typically goes unrecognized because the patient does not act out and interfere with care delivery like the patient with hyperactive delirium.
 - ▶ Often misdiagnosed
 - ▶ Patients typically exhibit lethargy, confusion, mutism, withdrawal, and apathy

Nasirideen A. Thomas, 2011

Types of Delirium

- ▶ **Mixed**
 - ▶ Displays signs and symptoms of both hyper- and hypoxic delirium
 - ▶ Can cycle between the two types of delirium

Wheeler & Thomas, 2011

What is the CAM-ICU Tool?

- ▶ The Confusion Assessment Method for the ICU (CAM-ICU) is a tool for assessing for the presence of delirium at the bedside.
- ▶ The 2015 clinical practice guidelines for Pain, Agitation, and Delirium (PAD) recommend that all Adult ICU patients be assessed for delirium regularly (i.e. once per shift).
- ▶ The CAM-ICU Tool is the most widely studied and used tool for assessing for delirium.
- ▶ The CAM-ICU Tool assessment takes less than 2 minutes to perform.
- ▶ The CAM-ICU Tool assesses all features of delirium.

(Sexton et al., 2012; Elie, 2011; Moore et al., 2011; Tronzo et al., 2012)

Understanding the types of and risk factors for delirium can lead to the question:

**Now what?
We have a wonderful tool
we can use.....**

How do I use the tool?

- ▶ Initiate the delirium assessment
- ▶ Determine the Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS) Score
- ▶ Feature 1 determines if delirium is acute onset or fluctuating course
- ▶ Assess whether or not the patient's mental status is different from baseline:
Yes - No

Using a valid and reliable tool improves detection of delirium among intubated and non-intubated ICU patients

(Elie, 2011; Moore Elie, Wheeler, & Grant, 2011; Speck, Rotek, Heban, & Reinos, 2009; Tronzo et al., 2012)

How do I use the tool?

- ▶ Proceed to Feature 2 which tests for inattention:
- ▶ Instruct the patient to squeeze your hand every time you say the letter A
- ▶ Then spell out SAWAHAART.
- ▶ Count how many times the letter A is mimed by the patient and score each time mimed as an error

How do I use the tool?

- ▶ Use the Pictures Test only if unable to complete Letters test.
- ▶ **Pictures Test:** Show pictures of a chair, key, table, shoes.
- ▶ Then pause for few minutes and show the same pictures with additional pictures inverted.
- ▶ Determine if the patient is able to recognize the original pictures.
- ▶ Instatation is present if score for either ASE: Letters or ASE: pictures is >2.

Application at bedside

Using this tool may take 3-4 minutes.

CAM-ICU test
Letters Attention Test

After you become familiar with the tool, it will take 2 minutes.

Click video to play

By, W (2012) Revised September 22, 2017 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC543134/>

How do I use the tool?

- ▶ Proceed to Delirium Assessment - Feature 3: Test for Altered Level of Consciousness (RASS)
- ▶ Proceed to Delirium Assessment - Feature 4: Test for Disorganized Thinking

DOCUMENTATION

This video demonstrates the step by step process of using the CAM-ICU Tool

Click the video to play

ICU Revised (2016, May 2017) Revised September 09, 2017, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC543134/> QITE

Sample of Meditech Charting

Perform RASS

Answer Feature 1 questions

References

MEHREZ, A. Z. & BARBER, M. E. (1997). *Water quality and the environment*. 2nd edn. London: Chapman & Hall.

MEHREZ, A. Z. & BARBER, M. E. (1998). *Water quality and the environment*. 3rd edn. London: Chapman & Hall.

MEHREZ, A. Z., BARBER, M. E. & BARBER, M. E. (1997). *Water quality and the environment*. 2nd edn. London: Chapman & Hall.

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MEHREZ, A. Z., BARBER, M. E. & BARBER, M. E. (1999). *Water quality and the environment*. 4th edn. London: Chapman & Hall.

APPENDIX F

Self-Learning Module Questions

1. Which feature of the CAM-ICU Tool determines if there is fluctuation in the mental status of the patient? **PPT Obj#4**

- a. Feature 1- Level of Cognition
- b. Feature 2- Inattention
- c. Feature 3- Level of Consciousness
- d. Feature 4- Disorganized Thinking

2. The CAM-ICU must be performed completely starting from Feature 1 to Feature 4 on all ICU patients no matter what Level of Consciousness is the patient in? **PPT Obj#4**

- a. True
- b. False

3. Which of the following are true about delirium? (circle all that apply)
PPT Obj#1

- a. Delirium has a rapid onset with a fluctuating course and includes inattention and clouded consciousness
- b. Delirium is characterized by an acute onset and fluctuating course of cognition which makes it difficult to process and recall information is impaired
- c. Delirium develops over a short period of time (hours to days), is usually reversible, and is a direct consequence of a medical condition
- d. Delirium is an acute state of mind and can be the result of medical conditions such as substance intoxication or withdrawal.

4. Identify the type of delirium in this scenario:

Mr. Smith was calm, quiet and responds when you called his name. He made two errors in identifying the ASE Letters. Now, two hours later, he is yelling, stating that someone is trying to kill him. PPT Obj#2

- a. Hyperactive
- b. Hypoactive
- c. Mixed

5. One of the effects of unrecognized delirium in ICU is a: PPT Obj#3

- a. Patient requiring restraints
- b. Prolonged hospital stay
- c. Poor PO intake

6. Which type of delirium typically goes unrecognized or is misdiagnosed? PPT Obj#2

- a. Hypoactive
- b. Mixed
- c. Hyperactive

7. To determine the Level of Cognition in Feature 1 of the CAM-ICU Tool, which of the following will you assess? PPT Obj#4

- a. Patient baseline mental status and fluctuations
- b. Patient history of dementia
- c. Patient level of awareness

8. ICU delirium is a predictor of which of the following? (Check all that apply) PPT Obj#3

- a. Increased Hospital Length of stay
- b. Increased Mortality
- c. Increased time on the ventilator and re-intubation
- d. Increased long-term cognitive impairment

9. In Feature 1 of the CAM ICU Tool, when do you use both letter and pictures on a patient? **PPT Obj#4**
- a. When patient is incapable of performing the letters
 - b. When the patient is non-English speaking
 - c. You must always perform both the letters and pictures
 - d. Never use the pictures
10. Which of the following features of delirium is assessed when instructing the patient to squeeze your hand every time the letter A is said in “SAVEAHAART”? **PPT Obj#4**
- a. Acute Changes in Cognition
 - b. Inattention
 - c. Disorganized Thinking
 - d. Altered Level of Consciousness

APPENDIX G

LAMINATED POCKET SIZE CAM-ICU

Front

STEP 1 RICHMOND AGITATION-SEDATION SCALE (RASS)
Sedation Assessment

Scale	Label	Description
+4	COMBATIVE	Combative, violent, immediate danger to staff
+3	VERY AGITATED	Pulls to remove tubes or catheters; aggressive
+2	AGITATED	Frequent non-purposeful movement, fights ventilator
+1	RESTLESS	Anxious, apprehensive, movements not aggressive
0	ALERT & CALM	Spontaneously pays attention to caregiver
-1	DROWSY	Not fully alert, but has sustained awakening to voice (eye opening & contact >10 sec)
-2	LIGHT SEDATION	Briefly awakens to voice (eyes open & contact <10 sec)

TOUCH (vertical text on right side of table)

If RASS is ≥ -2 proceed to CAM-ICU (Is patient CAM-ICU positive or negative?)

-3	MODERATE SEDATION	Movement or eye opening to voice (no eye contact)
-4	DEEP SEDATION	No response to voice, but movement or eye opening to physical stimulation
-5	UNAROUSEABLE	No response to voice or physical stimulation

If RASS is -3, -4 or -5 → STOP (patient unconscious), RECHECK later

Sessler, et al., Am J Respir Crit Care Med 2002; 166: 1338-1344 Eiv, et al., JAMA 2003; 286, 2983-2991

Back

STEP 2 Confusion Assessment Method for the ICU (CAM-ICU)
DELIRIUM ASSESSMENT

- Acute Change or Fluctuating Course of Mental Status:**
 - Is there an acute change from mental status baseline? **OR**
 - Has the patient's mental status fluctuated during the past 24 hours?

NO → CAM-ICU negative NO DELIRIUM

YES →
- Inattention:**
 - "Squeeze my hand when I say the letter 'A'."
 - Read the following sequence of letters: S A V E A H A A R T
 - ERRORS:** No squeeze with 'A' & Squeeze on letter other than 'A'
 - If unable to complete Letters → Pictures

0 - 2 Errors → CAM-ICU negative NO DELIRIUM

> 2 Errors →
- Altered Level of Consciousness**

Current RASS level (think back to sedation assessment in Step 1)

RASS other than zero → CAM-ICU positive DELIRIUM Present

RASS = zero →
- Disorganized Thinking:**
 - Will a stone float on water?
 - Are there fish in the sea?
 - Does one pound weigh more than two?
 - Can you use a hammer to pound a nail?

Command: "Hold up this many fingers" (Hold up 2 fingers)
"Now do the same thing with the other hand" (Do not demonstrate)
OR "Add one more finger" (If patient unable to move both arms)

> 1 Error → CAM-ICU positive DELIRIUM Present

0 - 1 Error → CAM-ICU negative NO DELIRIUM

APPENDIX H

LAMINATED ASE PICTURES

APPENDIX I

Practice Session with Feedback:

Staff one-to-one practice sessions

- The nurse will be required to complete the Delirium and CAM-ICU self-learning module and pass the post-test with a score of 84% prior to meeting with the author.
- During the practice session, the nurse is expected to correctly:
 - The nurse will enter the patient's room and introduce self.
 - Using the RASS scale, the nurse will determine the presence of agitation according to the scale.
 - If Feature 1 is absent (CAM-ICU is negative), the nurse will stop the assessment.
 - If positive, the nurse will evaluate Feature 2 (inattention) using the ASE Letters Score, or pictures if the patient is unable to respond.
 - If Feature 2 is negative, the nurse will evaluate Feature 3, Altered Level of Consciousness (ALOC).
 - The nurse will assess Feature 4 to determine if patient has disorganized thinking.
 - The nurse will ask Yes/No questions such as: Are there fish in the sea?
 - The nurse will also determine if patient is able to follow commands.
 - The nurse will document the results of the evaluation in Meditech.
- The author will provide feedback to the nurse during the training session.

APPENDIX J

Competency Check-off Procedure:

- The DNP author will evaluate the nurse application and use of the tool based on the competency checklist. (Please see attached checklist)
- If the nurse is not successful, another chance will be given to the nurse. On the third time, the unit manager will be informed.
- If the nurse is successful, she will be checked off in her competency on the use of the tool, and will be re-evaluated after one and three months.
- The competency on the use of the tool will be re-evaluated during the annual skills lab set by the hospital.

APPENDIX K

CAM-ICU tool Competency

Competency Validation Tool (CV)

Skills 2017

Name & Title: _____

Employee ID # _____

Department: _____

Validator: _____

Methods of Performance Demonstration: (check for all that apply)

DO RD Test CS Q&A SIM

Skills: DO Direct Observation RD Return Demonstration SIM Simulation

Knowledge: Test Post Test CS Case Study Review
Q&A Questions & Answers

Competency Period:

Initial 6 Months Review Annual Validator

Validation of Competency	
Check off each step of the competency as it is performed. All steps must be assessed and accurately demonstrated to achieve competency. Any incomplete or inaccurate performance requires an action plan below.	
<input type="radio"/>	Wash hands, introduce self to patient and explain to patient the reason of the visit.
<input type="radio"/>	Determine the Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale (RASS) Score of the patient
<input type="radio"/>	Demonstrate knowledge in different scales of RASS such as -3, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +3
<input type="radio"/>	Initiate Delirium assessment: Feature 1: determines if delirium is acute onset or fluctuating course
<input type="radio"/>	Determine if patient is different from baseline mental status : Yes - No
<input type="radio"/>	Determine any fluctuation in mental status in the last 24 hours : Yes-No
<input type="radio"/>	Proceed to Delirium Assessment - Feature 2: Test for Inattention
<input type="radio"/>	Instruct the patient to squeeze nurse hand every time letter A is said. Nurse will spell out SAVEAHAART
<input type="radio"/>	Count how many letter A is missed by the patient and score it as error
<input type="radio"/>	Test pictures score only if unable to complete Letters score.
<input type="radio"/>	Show pictures of chair, key, table, shoes. Then pause for few minutes.
<input type="radio"/>	Try to show the same pictures with additional objects. Ask patient if he remembers seeing the pictures.
<input type="radio"/>	Inattention is present if score for either ASE Letters or ASE pictures is >2
<input type="radio"/>	Proceed to Delirium Assessment - Feature 3: Test for Altered Level of Consciousness (RASS)
<input type="radio"/>	Proceed to Delirium Assessment - Feature 4: Test for Disorganized Thinking
<input type="radio"/>	Ask Yes-No Questions to patient: Do stones float on water?
<input type="radio"/>	Continue with Questions: Is one pound heavier than 2 pounds?

APPENDIX L

PROGRAM EVALUATION ROUNDING TOOL

Patient Audit Tool (48 hours of screening for 10 separate patients over a 2-week period)

1. Did the nurse screen the patient using CAM-ICU and document the results? (Yes/No)
2. At each data point, was the patient screened positive or negative?
3. Was the nursing plan of care changed related to positive screening? (Yes/No)

Patient Number: ____ (circle your responses)

Date	Day shift			Night shift			Notes
	CAM-ICU screen documented? Y/N	Positive/negative	If positive, nursing plan of care changed? Y/N	CAM-ICU screen documented? Y/N	Positive/negative	If positive, nursing plan of care changed? Y/N	
	CAM-ICU screen documented? Y/N	Positive/negative	If positive, nursing plan of care changed? Y/N	CAM-ICU screen documented? Y/N	Positive/negative	If positive, nursing plan of care changed? Y/N	